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The flow of energy and the momentum of a static electromagnetic field

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1. Introduction

The existence of a flow of energy and momentum in an electromagnetic wave is proved analytically due to the fact that the electromagnetic energy of an electromagnetic wave changes in time. The energy of a static field is constant in time. Therefore, the applicability of the formulas obtained for any field is not obvious. The formulas for the energy flux and momentum of a static electromagnetic field are analytically derived below.

2. The energy flux density of the electromagnetic field

2.1. Electromagnetic wave energy flux density

First, we consider a well-known method of obtaining a formula for the energy flux density of an electromagnetic wave [1, 2]. The density of electric and magnetic energy of a wave

$$W_e = \frac{\varepsilon\varepsilon_0}{2} E^2, \quad (1)$$

$$W_m = \frac{\mu\mu_0}{2} H^2. \quad (2)$$

The total density of electromagnetic wave energy

$$W = \frac{1}{2} (\varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E^2 + \mu\mu_0 H^2) \quad (3)$$

Because the

$$W_e = W_m \quad (3a)$$

from (1-3) we have:

$$E\sqrt{\varepsilon\varepsilon_0} = H\sqrt{\mu\mu_0}. \quad (3b)$$

Consequently,

$$W = \varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E^2 = \mu\mu_0 H^2 = EH\sqrt{\varepsilon\varepsilon_0\mu\mu_0} = EH/c. \quad (3c)$$

Further from (3) we have:

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\varepsilon\varepsilon_0}{2} E^2 + \frac{\mu\mu_0}{2} H^2 \right) = \left(\varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E \frac{dE}{dt} + \mu\mu_0 H \frac{dH}{dt} \right). \quad (4)$$

It follows from Maxwell's equations that

$$\text{rot}(\mathbf{E}) = -\mu\mu_0 \frac{d\mathbf{H}}{dt}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{rot}(\mathbf{H}) = \varepsilon\varepsilon_0 \frac{d\mathbf{E}}{dt}. \quad (6)$$

Consequently,

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = (-E\text{rot}(\mathbf{H}) + H\text{rot}(\mathbf{E})). \quad (7)$$

The law of conservation of field energy has the form

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = -\text{div}(\mathbf{S}). \quad (8)$$

The mathematical dependence of the form is known:

$$\text{div}(\mathbf{H} \times \mathbf{E}) = \mathbf{E} \cdot \text{rot}(\mathbf{H}) - \mathbf{H} \cdot \text{rot}(\mathbf{E}). \quad (9)$$

From (7-9) it follows that

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{H} \times \mathbf{E}. \quad (10)$$

From (3b, 10) we obtain

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{c}. \quad (10a)$$

2.2. The energy flux density of a moving body with a static electromagnetic field

Consider a design in which the electret and magnet create the vectors \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} . An example of such a design is an electret perpendicular to the magnet shown in Fig. 1a. In fig. 1c vectors of velocity \mathbf{V} , magnetic intensity \mathbf{H} , electric intensity \mathbf{E} , energy flux \mathbf{S} are shown.

Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1b.

In this design, a static electromagnetic field with a density of electromagnetic energy W occurs. If this body moves with speed v , then the energy moves at the same speed. According to the concept of Umov [3], this means that there is a flow of electromagnetic energy with a density

$$S = Wv. \tag{11}$$

In front of the frontal surface of a moving body, the intensities E and H change in time, i.e. derivatives of intensities exist $(\frac{dE}{dt}, \frac{dH}{dt})$. Therefore, the energy density W on the frontal surface of the body satisfies equation (4). To conserve energy, the density in other parts of the body must also change. These varying intensities satisfy Maxwell's equations (5, 6). From (4-6) follows, as shown in Section 2.1, equation (10). Thus, in the construction under consideration, conditions (10, 11) are satisfied.

The flow of energy is defined as

$$\bar{S} = Sb, \tag{12}$$

where b is the surface area emitting an energy flux. The flow \bar{S} is equal to the power P of the engine, which moves the body (in the absence of friction). Consequently,

$$S = \frac{P}{b}. \tag{13}$$

From (11, 13) we find the density of electromagnetic energy

$$W = \frac{P}{bv}. \tag{14}$$

and electromagnetic energy of body

$$\bar{W} = WV = \frac{PL}{v}. \quad (15)$$

where $V = Lb$ is body volume, L - body length. From (15, 3) we obtain:

$$\bar{W} = \frac{Lb}{2} (\varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E^2 + \mu\mu_0 H^2) \quad (16)$$

The kinetic energy of the body

$$\bar{W}_k = V \frac{mv^2}{2}, \quad (17)$$

where m is body weight. In the absence of friction, all engine power is spent on the creation of electromagnetic energy. Consequently,

$$\bar{W}_k = \bar{W} \quad (18)$$

From (16-18) we obtain:

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} = \frac{V}{2} (\varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E^2 + \mu\mu_0 H^2)$$

or

$$\frac{\rho v^2}{vg} = (\varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E^2 + \mu\mu_0 H^2) \quad (19)$$

A moving body with a static electromagnetic field can be considered as **a moving packet of a static electromagnetic field**. The energy and energy flow (i.e. power) of this package remains constant.

The power of the engine which moves the body is partly the power of the package, and partly can be spent on the compensation of mechanical losses and other needs.

Formula (19) means that the density of the mechanical energy of the body is equal to the density of the electromagnetic energy of a moving packet of a static electromagnetic field. Thus, in a moving body with a static electromagnetic field, the conversion of mechanical energy into electromagnetic energy of a static electromagnetic field occurs.

In the static flow of electromagnetic energy, there is no conversion of magnetic energy into electrical energy and vice versa, and therefore there is no equality between the terms.

Let be

$$\frac{E}{H} = \beta. \quad (20)$$

From (19, 20) we find:

$$\frac{\rho v^2}{g} = H^2 (\varepsilon\varepsilon_0 \beta^2 + \mu\mu_0). \quad (21)$$

or

$$\frac{\rho v^2}{g} = E^2 \left(\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 + \frac{\mu \mu_0}{\beta^2} \right). \quad (21a)$$

For $\beta < 10^{-3}$ we have

$$\frac{\rho v^2}{g} \approx \mu \mu_0 H^2 = BH. \quad (22)$$

For $\beta > 10^3$ we have

$$\frac{\rho v^2}{g} \approx \varepsilon \varepsilon_0 E^2 = DE. \quad (22a)$$

Example 1.

In [7], a “Device for converting an electromagnetic momentum into a mechanical momentum” was proposed, in which such a package is created. In this device, a moving magnet creates electrical intensities

$$E = vB = vH\mu\mu_0. \quad (23)$$

Then

$$\beta = \frac{E}{H} = v\mu\mu_0. \quad (24)$$

From (21a, 23) we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\rho v}{g} &= E^2 \left(\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 + \frac{\mu \mu_0}{\beta^2} \right) = E^2 \left(\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 + \frac{\mu \mu_0}{(v\mu\mu_0)^2} \right) \\ &= \varepsilon \varepsilon_0 E^2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 \mu \mu_0 v^2} \right) = \varepsilon \varepsilon_0 E^2 \left(\left(\frac{c}{v} \right)^2 + 1 \right) \approx \varepsilon \varepsilon_0 E^2 \left(\frac{c}{v} \right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

From (21, 23) we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\rho v^2}{g} &= H^2 (\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 \beta^2 + \mu \mu_0) = \mu \mu_0 H^2 (\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 \mu \mu_0 v^2 + 1) = \\ &= \mu \mu_0 H^2 \left(\left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^2 + 1 \right) \approx \mu \mu_0 H^2 = HB. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

From (25, 26) we find:

$$\frac{\rho v^2}{g} \approx \varepsilon \varepsilon_0 E^2 \left(\frac{c}{v} \right)^2 \approx \mu \mu_0 H^2. \quad (26a)$$

Find more

$$\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 E^2 = \varepsilon \varepsilon_0 (vH\mu\mu_0)^2 = H^2 \left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^2, \quad (27)$$

i.e. electrical energy can be neglected, i.e. packet energy density

$$W = HB. \quad (28)$$

We also note that from (23, 28) it follows:

$$S = EH = vBH, \quad (29)$$

which coincides with formula (11).

2.3. Static electromagnetic field energy flux density

Formula (10) can be applied to a static electromagnetic field. Feynman in [1] describes a speculative experiment in which an electric charge and magnet are located side by side. It is stated that in consequence (10), a stream of electromagnetic energy circulates around this pair. Another example is a DC wire, which creates a static electromagnetic field. The flow of electromagnetic energy also circulates in this field, due to the existence of dependence (10). However, there is no evidence of the applicability of formula (10) for a static electromagnetic field.

We again use the formula (11). In a static electromagnetic field, we know the electromagnetic energy density W and the electromagnetic energy flux density S . Therefore, we can determine the energy flux rate

$$v = W/S. \quad (30)$$

In [8], some phenomena are substantiated on the basis of the existence of a flow of electromagnetic energy in a static field. In [8, chapter 5] on this basis, it is proved that the flow of energy in a direct current wire moves inside the wire (and not outside it). In [8, chapter 5a], on this basis, the operation of Milroy's engine is explained. In [8, chapter 7] on this basis, it is shown that a flow of electromagnetic energy circulates in a charged capacitor and this explains the nature of the potential energy of the capacitor.

3. The momentum of the electromagnetic field

3.1. Electromagnetic momentum of the wave

First, consider the well-known method of obtaining the formula for the momentum density of an electromagnetic wave [4]. The momentum density is determined from the assumption that the energy of an electromagnetic plane wave incident perpendicularly to the flat surface of a weakly conducting body with dielectric and magnetic permeabilities equal to unity is converted into the thermal energy of the current excited in this body by this wave. It turns out that

$$J_o = W/c. \quad (31)$$

It is important to note that J_o is a scalar quantity, not a vector.

In the system of Maxwell equations, Maxwell himself included an equation of the form [5]

$$B = \text{rot}(A). \quad (32)$$

Maxwell calls quantity A either an electromagnetic pulse at a point or a vector potential of electric currents. Currently, this equation is not included in the list of initial equations but is derived from the equation

$$\operatorname{div}(B) = 0 \quad (33)$$

and famous identity

$$\operatorname{div}(\operatorname{rot}(A)) = 0 \quad (34)$$

The value A is called the vector potential, and the electromagnetic momentum is called that which has the dimension of a mechanical electromagnetic momentum and is defined above. What Maxwell had in mind when speaking of an "electromagnetic momentum at a point" remains unclear. It can be assumed that Maxwell did not have time to finish the thought. In the 80s of the last century, it was said that "God himself wrote with the hand of Maxwell" [6].

We multiply both sides of equation (32) by the electric induction vector D . Then we get:

$$B \times D = \operatorname{rot}(A \times D). \quad (35)$$

It can be noted that these quantities have the dimension of momentum density. Therefore, the **vector-momentum**

$$J = \operatorname{rot}(A \times D), \quad (36)$$

we will continue to call the density of electromagnetic field and quantity (31) is the **modulus of this vector**. So, from (35, 36) we get:

$$J = B \times D. \quad (37)$$

Electric and magnetic induction

$$D = \varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E, \quad B = \mu\mu_0 H. \quad (38)$$

From (36, 37, 10) we obtain:

$$\varepsilon\varepsilon_0\mu\mu_0 S = J \quad (39)$$

or we get the well-known formula

$$\frac{S}{c^2} = J. \quad (40)$$

A momentum propagates along with a stream of energy at the same speed.

3.2. The momentum of a moving body with a static electromagnetic field

So, the pulse propagates with the speed of energy flow and is determined by (40). This ratio can be extended to any flow speed. Therefore, it can be applied to the flow of a static electromagnetic field existing in a body moving with a speed v . In this case

$$J = \frac{S}{v^2}. \quad (41)$$

From (41, 30) we obtain:

$$J = \frac{Wv}{v^2}. \quad (42)$$

From (41, 11) we obtain:

$$J = \frac{S}{v^2} = \frac{Wv}{v} = \frac{W}{v}. \quad (43)$$

Electromagnetic momentum

$$\bar{J} = J\mathcal{V}, \quad (44)$$

where \mathcal{V} is the volume of the electromagnetic field. Suppose that volume \mathcal{V} and body volume are the same. Then from (43, 44) we find:

$$\bar{J} = \frac{W}{v}\mathcal{V}. \quad (45)$$

It follows from the law of conservation of momentum that when an electromagnetic momentum appears, the body acquires an oppositely directed mechanical momentum

$$\bar{M} = -\bar{J}. \quad (46)$$

Therefore, the vector \bar{M} has the direction of the vector $(-S)$, its module

$$|\bar{M}| = \frac{W}{v}\mathcal{V}. \quad (47)$$

or

$$|\bar{M}| = \frac{\bar{W}}{v}, \quad (48)$$

where \bar{W} is the electromagnetic energy of the body

$$\bar{W} = W\mathcal{V}. \quad (49)$$

Example 2.

We continue in Example 1. From (17, 18) we find

$$\bar{W} = \bar{W}_K = \frac{vmv^2}{2} \quad (50)$$

From (48, 50) we find

$$|\bar{M}| = \frac{vmv}{2}. \quad (51)$$

3.3. The momentum of a static electromagnetic field

In this case, from (30, 41) we obtain

$$J = \frac{S}{v^2} = \frac{S}{(s/W)^2} = \frac{W^2}{s}. \quad (52)$$

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